

DESIGN OF PHOTOTHERMAL TRIGGERED BILAYER MORPHING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents finite element method (FEM) modelling of a bilayered shape-morphing composite, triggered by photo-thermal stimulus. The bilayer consists of an upper-layer of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) reinforced chitosan-methacrylamide (rGO-chitosanMA) and a lower-layer of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). The FEM model is experimentally validated and exploited in two case studies that predict shape-morphing for various thickness ratios of upper- to lower-layer. Case one is a parametric study of a bilayer with constant thickness, where the upper-layer thickness is varying from 1 to 99% of the total thickness. In case 2 the upper-layer thickness varies from 1 to 20 μm increasing by 1 μm , while the lower ply thickness varies from 50 to 100 μm increasing by 2 μm . The results describe the shape-morphing trend of the bilayered composite when the upper- to lower-layer thickness ratio changes, and demonstrate a method of designing composite bilayers with triggered and predictable morphing response with potential applications in soft robotics and artificial muscles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reversible shape-morphing composites are material systems that change shape when an external stimulus is applied and recover after it is removed. Bilayered composites achieve shape-morphing when the strain across the thickness differs under the same level of stimulus [1]. The differential strain generates stress in the interface and the shape-morphing composite bends towards the layer with smaller strain [2].

Certain triggers, such as liquid and moisture, require physical contact and diffusion into the material so the shape-morphing is constrained by the contact area and the diffusion rate [3]. Electric and mechanical triggering allow accurate control of the shape-morphing and can be applied in localized areas; however, the mobility of the systems is constrained by the connections [4], [5]. Triggers such as light and heat can be applied remotely and in localized areas; moreover, the shape-morphing response is typically in seconds [6], [7].

Shape-morphing composites have potential application in soft robotics, sensors, actuators, and artificial muscles [8]–[10]. A comprehensive characterization of their morphing behaviour is essential

for optimal use and design. Physical testing and characterization is costly and time consuming; whilst, computational simulation approaches allow the analysis of shape-morphing composites for a wide range of scenarios at relatively low cost and time.

Here a computational study of a photo-thermal triggered bilayered shape-morphing composite is presented. This system is made of a lower-layer of surface modified polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) with the upper-layer of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) reinforced chitosan-methacrylamide (rGO-chitosanMA). Difference in their coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) drives shape-morphing in this system; the CTE for rGO-chitosanMA and PDMS are $-100 \mu\epsilon \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and $322 \mu\epsilon \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, respectively. These values were previously determined by the authors using dilatometry [11]. Photo-thermal triggering is allowed by exploiting rGO absorption of infrared radiation [12]. Delamination is prevented by creating a covalent bond between the surface-modified PDMS and functionalized rGO-chitosanMA via thiol-ene click reaction [13].

A multi-physics finite element (FE) model was created to simulate shape-morphing for different thickness ratios of rGO-chitosanMA layer to PDMS layer. Comparisons between simulations and experiments are performed to validate assumptions and simplifications made in the FE model.

2 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

A 3D FE model of the bilayered shape-morphing composite was created in Abaqus. The model assumes rectangular cross section (Figure 1A) and employs 3D brick shape finite elements that have the following characteristics: 20 nodes, reduced integration, hybrid formulation, quadratic displacement and linear temperature; they are identified in Abaqus by the name C3D20RHT. This type of element effectively simulates thermal expansion and bending without shear locking and hour glassing, so excessive element deformation and stiffness are avoided.

A mesh sensitivity analysis was carried out for the tip displacement (distance between the initial and final position of the free end). Model dimensions were 6 mm in length and 1 mm in width; the total bilayer thickness was 90 μm of which 10 μm corresponded to the rGO-chitosanMA layer and 80 μm to the PDMS layer. Tip displacement value converged for a mesh density of 30 elements along the length (L), 5 elements across the width (W) and 2 elements through the thickness (t) of each layer (**Error! Reference source not found.B**). However, the model is used in simulations where the rGO-chitosanMA layer is as thin as 1 μm ; this though results to a larger element aspect ratio that might cause errors. For this reason, the mesh density was reduced to 30 x 5 x 1 elements (LxWxt). This mesh density simulates 99% of the convergence value for tip displacement at the lowest computational cost compared with meshes with higher mesh density.

Figure 1: (A) Schematic diagram of the bilayered shape-morphing composite model (not in scale). (B)

Results of the mesh sensitivity analysis for the tip displacement; the legend indicates the number of elements along the thickness of each layer and the *horizontal-axis* shows the number of elements along length and width (e.g. 12x1 L x W).

Kinematic boundary conditions are zero translations at the fixed end of the model (Figure 1A). The trigger is simulated as a transient increase of temperature uniformly distributed across the bilayer. Both materials are considered linear elastic with Young's moduli of 1.52 GPa and 1.28 MPa for rGO-chitosanMA and PDMS, respectively. Moreover, the materials are assumed to be homogeneous isotropic to simplify the stress analysis and reduce the computational time. Mechanical and thermal properties of both materials are assumed to be constant during the simulations. The interface, although more complex in the physical system, in the analysis it is modelled by tying the degrees of freedom of the nodes at the contact faces of the two layers. The model also accounts for geometric non-linear effects (large deflections).

Two parametric studies are conducted to investigate the thickness ratio effect on the shape-morphing behaviour. The model for the bilayer parametric studies is 6 mm long and 1 mm width; these dimensions are within the range of values where the model was experimentally validated. In Case 1, the thickness of the bilayered shape-morphing composite is fixed at 100 μm and the thickness of the rGO-chitosanMA layer varies between 1 and 99 μm in increments of 1 μm . In Case 2, the minimum and maximum bilayer thicknesses are 51 μm and 120 μm , respectively; thickness of the rGO-chitosanMA layer varies between 1 and 20 μm in increments of 1 μm , while the thickness of the PDMS layer varies between 50 and 100 μm in increments of 2 μm . The trigger is an increase of temperature 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in both cases.

The model was validated with experimental data from three repeat experiments. Each experiment was done on a different sample. Dimensions of the samples and increments of temperature were used as inputs for the corresponding simulations of each experiment.

3 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

3.1. Materials

Chitosan (medium molecular weight), methacrylic anhydride, (3-mercaptopropyl)trimethoxysilane (MPTMS), 2-hydroxy-4'-(2-hydroxyethoxy)-2-methylpropiophenone (Irgacure 2959), L-ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and all chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (UK). Graphite (grade: 2369) was supplied by Graphexel Ltd (UK), and PDMS (Sylgard184) was purchased from Dow Corning.

3.2. Samples preparation

3.2.1. PDMS film preparation and thiolation

Briefly, PDMS was mixed with its crosslinker in a 10:1 weight ratio of PDMS to crosslinker, and centrifuged at 175 RCF for 3 min to degas it. Thin PDMS films were produced by spin coating at 800 rpm for 1 min (Spin Coater, WS-400B, Laurell, USA) onto a polystyrene petri dish, and then cured in an oven at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight. One face of the PDMS film was low temperature and low pressure plasma treated in air for 5 min to increase the number of polar groups on the surface to downstream thiolation by MPTMS. The plasma treated surface was thiolated by immersing the film in 10 wt% MPTMS in ethyl acetate solution and orbitally shaken at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 h (Lab Companion SI-600, South Korea). Post thiolation, the functionalized PDMS film was rinsed twice with methanol and dichloromethane at room temperature (RT). The PDMS thiolated surface was dried with nitrogen gas prior to photocrosslinking with rGO-chitosanMA.

3.2.2. rGO-chitosanMA preparation

Chitosan powder (2 wt%) was added to a 0.5 M solution of acetic acid in deionized (DI) water and magnetically stirred overnight at RT. Chitosan was functionalised by adding 0.4 molar equivalents of methacrylic anhydride dropwise for 3 h at RT under constant stirring. The functionalized chitosan was dialyzed against DI water for one week with constant water changes and subsequently freeze-dried for

further use [13]. Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared via the modified Hummer's method [14]. GO aqueous solution (0.2 mg/ml) was reduced using vitamin C (0.02 wt.%) under ammonia controlled alkali condition (pH: 9-10) at 95 °C for 15 min [15]. Freeze dried functionalized chitosan was weighed and added into DI water under magnetic stirring. rGO solution was added dropwise into chitosanMA solution under magnetic stirring until the concentration of chitosanMA was 2 wt%.

3.2.3. Bilayer preparation

Photo initiator was added to the rGO-chitosanMA solution until the concentration was 1 wt%. A film of rGO-chitosanMA solution was then manually flow-coated over the PDMS thiolated face and photo-crosslinked under UV light in air for 5 min (Spectroline SB-100P/FB, 365 nm UV lamp, USA). The bilayer was washed with DI water to remove the any unreacted rGO-chitosanMA, followed by drying in an oven at 25 °C overnight.

4 MORPHING EVALUATION

Experimental morphing was evaluated on three samples prepared with the method described in section 3.2.3. Sample 1 was 3 mm in length and 86 µm in thickness; in which 4 µm of the thickness corresponded to the rGO-chitosanMA layer and 82 µm to the PDMS layer. Sample 2 was 4 mm in length and 90 µm in thickness, with 7 µm thick rGO-chitosanMA layer and 83 µm thick PDMS layer. Sample 3 was 8 mm long and 90 µm in thickness with a 7 µm thick rGO-chitosanMA layer.

In order to assess morphing, one end of the sample was clamped using a wooden clip (to minimize heat conductance away from the sample) while an infrared (IR) bulb (Philips R125, 300 W, South Korea) was turned on to photo-thermally trigger sample morphing. The change of temperature was recorded with an IR camera (Flir A35, USA) and the shape-morphing captured using a digital camera (Panasonic DMC-FH2, Japan) (Figure 2). The tip displacement of the unconstrained end was determined by image analysis. The sample bends and twists (Figure 3A) during the triggering so the experimental tip displacement was measured in the middle point along the width (Figure 3A).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the experimental setup to test the bilayer shape-morphing behaviour.

The starting and final temperatures of the photo-thermally triggered shape-morphing samples were obtained from IR camera recordings and applied as triggers to the corresponding models in an effort to match simulations and experiments conditions (Figure 3B).

Figure 3: (A) Overlay images of the initial and final shape of sample 3. (B) Infrared thermography showing the temperature distribution in the bilayer shape-morphing composite before (left) and after (right) triggering.

The relative error (RE) of the simulation with respect to the experiment is calculated as percentage using equation 1.

$$RE = \left| \frac{\text{experimental result} - \text{simulation result}}{\text{experimental result}} \right| \times 100 \quad (1)$$

5 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Discussion

Tip displacement of the shape-morphing composite is estimated by the FEM model simulations with a relative error of 10.3, 7.0 and 10.2 % for samples 1, 2 and 3, respectively (Figure 4B). The FEM model simulations here consistently overestimate the tip displacement (Figure 4A). This error is deemed acceptable for predicting the shape-morphing behaviour for different thickness ratios.

Figure 4: Comparison of simulation and experimental data; Sample 1 is labelled S1 in the plots; the same labelling convention is used for samples 2 and 3. (A) Measured tip displacement and corresponding simulated tip displacement of three samples. (B) Relative error (RE) of the simulation respect to measured tip displacement.

Infrared thermography data demonstrates that the temperature distribution in sample is non uniform (Figure 3B); the temperature at the constrained end is ~ 5 °C higher than the free end. Temperature distribution in the FEM model is modelled as uniform; this might be one of the sources of difference between the simulations and the experiments. Applying the sample temperature distribution to the FEM model might reduce the relative error of the simulations in comparison to experiments, a trade-off against long computational time.

Other sources of error can be the introduction of defects during manufacture and non-homogeneity of the materials. The model assumes uniform thicknesses; in contrast, the samples might have thickness variations that can have a large effect in the shape-morphing as the parametric studies show. The PDMS layer is prone to air bubbles, trapped during film preparation, which cannot escape due to the high viscosity of the material. The rGO-chitosanMA layer is prone to have defects such as rGO aggregations and porosity due to air entrapment. A correction factor could be used in the material properties; in this way the model could account for some of the sample defects.

Results of the first parametric study showed that the tip displacement sharply increases when the rGO-chitosanMA layer is less than 30% of the total bilayer thickness (Figure 5A). Tip displacement has a plateau if the rGO-chitosanMA layer is in the range from 50 to 99% of the total bilayer thickness; in this range, tip displacement is very small compared with the bilayer length so the deformation of the shape-morphing composite is negligible.

Second parametric study (Case 2) predicts the shape-morphing behaviour of the bilayer for wider range of bilayer thickness values compared with the first parametric study (Case 1). The plot obtained with the results (Figure 5B) can be used as a guide for designing a shape-morphing composite that achieves a specific tip displacement. Maximum deformation is achieved when the rGO-chitosanMA layer is 1 μm and the PDMS layer is 50 μm in thickness. Contrary, if the rGO-chitosanMA layer is 20 μm and the PDMS layer is 50 μm in thickness, tip displacement is negligible with respect to the bilayer length.

Figure 5: (A) Results of the parametric study for Case 1 showing the trend of the tip displacement for different percentage of upper-layer in total thickness of the bilayer. (B) Results of the parametric study for Case 2. The surface plot depicts the magnitude of tip displacement for different thickness ratios of upper-layer to lower-layer. Colour bar units represent mm.

5.2. Concluding remarks

The photo-thermal shape-morphing of a bilayered composite was successfully modelled by FEM. The FEM numerical simulations were compared with experimental data to validate simplifications made. Simulation accuracy is deemed to be acceptable for using the FEM model in studies that predict the tip displacement of a shape-morphing cantilever composite beam, as investigated here. Two parametric studies were performed; the results can be used to optimize layer geometry and material physical properties with the aim to achieve in a controllable manner the desired shape-morphing configuration of complex systems used in a variety of applications including soft robotics, artificial muscles, sensors and actuators.

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